

FATIGUE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF MWCNT REINFORCED GFRP COMPOSITES WITH SURFACE ARTIFICIAL DEFECTS

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ABSTRACT

The present work investigates the effect of artificial surface defects of glass fiber reinforced polymers (GFRP) under constant amplitude fatigue loadings for a number of nano-reinforced matrices. Different concentrations of Multi-Wall Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs) were added to the epoxy resin before vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) manufacturing of the composites. Different composite plates were made with different MWCNTs concentrations, namely 0.5, 0.75 and 3.0 wt%. The composite plates had 10 plies of unidirectional S-glass fabric with the resin used being a typical one used in aeronautics, the Araldite LY 564. The specimens were cut from the material plates according to ASTM D3039 and were edge-polished. Electrical cable connectors were attached to the specimen's surface to record the electrical resistance change during mechanical testing. The artificial surface notches were introduced with a precise saw cut and the notch depth was measured with image analysis. Two regions of the specimen were monitored with electrical resistance change; the so-called "healthy" region and the "notched" region that had the artificial notch. On the opposite flat surface of the coupon, strain gauges were attached and the readings of strain gauges and electrical resistance were continuously recorded during fatigue. Fatigue tests were performed in a servo hydraulic MTS 100 kN loading frame with a constant stress ratio of $R = 0.1$. Three different fatigue maximum stress levels were applied to address all fatigue regimes. One aim of this work was to assess the composites monitoring capabilities for different concentration of wt % MWCNTs in the resin matrix. Another was to identify the monitoring capabilities of the same composites under artificial defects for constant amplitude fatigue tests. It was found that a sudden increase takes place on the transition of stage III of the fatigue mechanism. This sudden increase in the resistance change was applied maximum stress dependant, ranging from 83% for the low applied stress fatigue tests up to approximately 40% for the high applied stress fatigue tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer composites have a strong demand in the aerospace industry sector during the last decades. The use of multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) in polymer composites has attracted great attention nowadays due to their excellent mechanical and electrical properties. Using a modified resin doped with MWCNTs, a non-conductive GFRP composite is now able to become electrically conductive. Accordingly, exploiting the electrical resistance change methodology introduced by Baron and Schulte [1], GFRPs are now capable to be monitored by measuring simultaneously surface electrical resistance change of a specimen during its mechanical loading. Consequently, the addition of electrically conductive MWCNTs offers to non-conductive GFRP composites the potential for sensing

capability through electrical resistance changes on the onset of damage [2, 3] and enhanced fracture properties e.g. [4, 5].

Research on these innovative, multi-functional materials is mainly based on the enhancement of their mechanical performance as well as measurements of electrical resistance change simultaneously recorded from stress/strain variances of the testing specimens, e.g. [5, 6]. Nevertheless, it is scarcely reported in the open literature their mechanical/electrical response under cyclic mechanical loadings or even fatigue loadings.

2 COMPOSITES MANUFACTURING

The resin used was a typical epoxy resin used in the aeronautics, Araldite LY 564. It was selected primarily due to its low viscosity and high mechanical properties. For each different case, resin of approximate 400 g and different percentages of carbon nanotubes were mixed in the dissolver. Use of a Torrus Mill dissolver was preferred since it introduces high shear forces by a high speed rotating disc and the compound is stirred in a vacuum container to avoid air inclusions. Dissolver's mixing time of the resin with the different percentages of MWCNTs, namely 0.5 wt%, 0.75 wt% and 3.0 wt% lasted more than 24 h each. Resin was then mixed with the catalyst (Aradur 2954 by Huntsman) and was placed on open metallic moulds and in the shape of a typical tensile specimen.

For the manufacturing of the composite plate, the following process was followed: 10 plies of glass fiber fabric (style 6781, S2 glass by Fiber Glast Developments Corporation), oriented at 0/90° had been cut at the required dimensions (300 x 300 mm). The plies were laid and the wrap faces were alternated upwards and downwards during the lay-up, resulting in a cross-ply balanced and symmetric laminate. Resin with different percentages of carbon nanotubes, prepared from the previous section, was used to manufacture the composites with the same lay-up sequence. Vacuum infusion method had been used to manufacture the plates of the material. Appropriate bagging material was placed, vacuum was then applied and the infusion of the resin followed, Figure 1. The manufactured plates were thereafter cured for 2 hours at 60°C followed by a 4 hour at 120°C post cure, as recommended by the resin manufacturer's data sheet.

Figure 1: Manufacturing process of the hybrid composites with the vacuum infusion method.

According to the ASTM D3039 specification the tensile specimens had been cut from the material plates and edge-polished. The dimensions of the testing specimens were width x length = 25 mm x 250 mm.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Electrical cable connectors were attached to the specimen's surface, Figure 2. The cables were connected to the Agilent multimeter and the initial electrical resistance of the reference test section was measured. The electrical cable connectors were attached in two regions of the specimen (healthy and notched, respectively) in order to record their electrical resistance change during mechanical testing.

Figure 2: Photograph of a specimen with a formed surface artificial notch and electrical cable connectors.

The artificial surface notches were introduced by a precise saw cut and the notch depth was measured with image analysis. Two regions of the specimen were monitored by the electrical resistance change method; the so-called “healthy” region and the “notched” region that had the presence of the artificial notch, as can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Specimen with two measuring areas: (a) notched and (b) healthy.

On the opposite flat surface of the coupon, strain gauges were attached and the readings of strain gauges and electrical resistance were continuously recorded in a PC during the progressive fatigue cycles. The first target of the present work is to assess the composites’ monitoring capabilities for different concentration wt% MWCNTs in the resin matrix. The last target is to seek the monitoring capabilities of the same composites under the presence of an artificial notch and during the constant amplitude fatigue tests.

Fatigue tests were performed in a servohydraulic MTS 100 kN loading frame with a constant stress ratio of $R = 0.1$. Three different fatigue stress levels were investigated to address different fatigue regimes, Table 1. The gross applied force was calculated to be equivalent for axial stress of 275, 185 and 125 MPa for the healthy region, while this force was translated to higher stress level for the notched regions and according to the decrease of the composite’s cross-section.

Gauge area	Maximum applied stress (MPa)		
	Notched	400	275
Healthy	275	185	125

Table 1: Different fatigue stress levels investigated.

4 RESULTS

Figure 4 shows the results of the electrical resistance change of the two gauge areas under constant amplitude fatigue loading till fracture for the case of 0.75 wt% MWCNTs composite. It can be seen that in the notched area the electrical readings have higher values than the respective healthy area and for the same applied fatigue cycles. For the case of the healthy area, an almost linear increase in electrical resistance change is noticed with increasing fatigue life. For the case of the notched area, this almost linear correlation is evident up to almost 50% fatigue lifetime, while an exponential trend is noticed. The electrical readings of the notched area are well higher than the respective initial values and this is evidence of continuously introduced damage in that region.

Figure 4: Diagram of fatigue maximum and minimum electrical resistance change values as a function of fatigue cycles for the case of maximum applied stress of 275 MPa for 0.75% wt MWCNTs.

Figure 5 shows that the electrical resistance change in the notched area is greater than in the healthy region after 50% of the specimens' lifetime. The respective electrical resistance change values of the notched region increased gradually and an essential sharp increase of around 90% was noticed. As can be seen in Figure 6, the specimen failed at the artificial notch region after 227,283 fatigue cycles.

Figure 5: Diagram of fatigue maximum and minimum electrical resistance change values as a function of fatigue cycles for the case of maximum applied stress of 275 MPa for 3.0% wt MWCNTs.

Figure 6: Specimens (left: 0.75 wt% MWCNTs and right: 3.0 wt% MWCNTs) of the previous figures after failure in the notched gauge area.

Figure 7 shows the electrical resistance change curves of three specimens of the same material (0.75 wt% MWCNTs) tested under different maximum tensile stress, namely 185, 275 and 400 MPa at the notched area. It can be noticed that the electrical resistance change increases significantly for all cases; increased electrical resistance values are recorded after 80% of fatigue lifetime for the case of the low-applied stress regime; for the higher stress regime, this sudden increase is noticed only after 65% of fatigue lifetime. Finally, for the heavily stressed specimen, electrical resistance change values show an essential increase only after 45% that is evident of irreversible, permanent matrix cracking damage.

Figure 7: Diagrams of maximum and minimum electrical resistance change values over fatigue life different applied maximum stresses, namely 400, 275 and 185 MPa for specimens reinforced with 0.75 wt% MWCNTs.

Figure 8 shows the respective curves for the case of specimens reinforced with 3.00 wt% MWCNTs. Almost the same qualitative results can be noticed for this case with the exception of the poorest screening of the electrical resistance values.

Figure 8: Diagrams of maximum and minimum electrical resistance change values over fatigue life different applied maximum stresses, namely 400, 275 and 185 MPa for specimens reinforced with 3.0 wt% MWCNTs.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions drawn from the present work can be summarized as follows:

- notched regions exhibit higher electrical resistance change values that respective healthy for all materials and applied maximum stress regions,
- composite reinforced with 0.75 wt% MWCNTs showed higher screening of electrical resistance change values, and
- matrix cracking damage can be identified with progressive fatigue damage and can be assessed for the different applied maximum stresses.

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